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Modernization of production processes control system: models of efficiency assessment

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Studying methods of modernizing production management in the framework of digital transformation aims to identify strategies to improve the performance of production systems and their adaptability to changes in the external environment.

The article aims to develop comprehensive methodological approaches to managing production processes by integrating mathematical analysis, digital technologies, and adaptive management solutions.

Materials and methods. Optimization modeling, cluster analysis, and econometric calculations were used to achieve the research objectives. Analytical models, including adaptability coefficient, digitalization indicator, and stress-testing methodology were proposed for assessing the sustainability of production systems. Software implementation used Python and libraries for data processing and predictive analysis.

Research results. The developed analytical tools were tested on a sample of data collected from enterprises of different industries. The adaptability coefficient demonstrated the stability of production systems in market volatility, and the digitalization indicator confirmed the efficiency of investments in digital infrastructure. The stress testing methodology revealed the key points of production systems sensitivity to changes in market and technological factors.

Conclusion. The application of the developed models allows optimizing the management of production, improve the sustainability of systems and increase their efficiency. The developed methodology forms the basis for further improvement of management strategies in technological progress and digital transformation conditions.

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INTRODUCTION

Intensification of technological progress and digital transformation of economic processes place increased demands on managing production systems. Methods based on linear planning and unification of operations show decreasing performance under conditions of high market volatility and tightening of product quality standards. Managing production processes requires applying methodologies that combine digital technologies, formalized mathematical analysis, and intelligent algorithms to ensure the adaptation of systems to highly dynamic environments [1; 2].

Complex manufacturing systems depend on various interrelated factors that affect their functionality. The key challenges include rationalization of resource utilization, minimization of production costs, and optimization of the time characteristics of operations. The main difficulties are excessive resource consumption, reduced production capacity, and flexibility in changing environmental parameters. To overcome these challenges, analytical approaches based on data processing methods, numerical modeling and mathematical optimization are required.

Applying digital technologies in managing production opens up prospects for their qualitative transformation. Predictive analytics, logistics optimization, and cost reduction through automated control systems are key areas of this approach. However, implementing these technologies involves several difficulties, including modernizing production facilities, developing personnel competencies, and developing mathematically based models for data analysis and decision support [3].

This research aims to create and implement mathematical models and digital tools to transform manufacturing management and seeks to develop methods that help improve the efficiency of manufacturing systems and their compliance with the requirements of the digital economy.

Literature review

The analysis of literary sources covers a wide range of issues related to transformation of production management of – the work by I. I. Rakhmeeva [4] is devoted the methodology of diagnosing the region's innovation infrastructure. The author studies the impact of innovative approaches on the effectiveness of production management and describes the mechanisms of adaptation of enterprises to dynamic changes in the external environment. The study emphasizes the importance of using a system approach focused on integrating innovative solutions into organizational structures.

The study by L. E. Dubanevich et al. [5] presents the concept of improving the methods of assessing the efficiency of innovative enterprises. The primary attention is paid to analytical approaches based on data processing and integration of digital technologies into management systems. The work offers efficiency assessment models that consider the synergetic interaction of economic and technological factors.

In the paper, J. Lee et al. [6] discuss intelligent algorithms, data analytics, and innovation in the context of Industry 4.0. The authors emphasize creating intelligent control systems that use big data analytics. The study reveals the prospects for implementing digital technologies that optimize management and increase the adaptability of production systems.

A. V. Kubarsky et al. [7] and E. N. Vakhrusheva et al. [8] analyze the use of performance indicators (KPI) to evaluate and manage production. They consider methods of developing monitoring systems that ensure process transparency and validity of management decisions. The studies emphasize the universality of the proposed approaches in various industries and agriculture.

The articles by A. A. Zaitsev, N. D. Dmitriev [9], and D. G. Rodionov et al. [10] analyze the application of stress testing to assess production systems stability. The authors consider methods of identifying critical points of the system that allow developing an adaptive management strategy. The research reveals the potential of stress testing to develop sustainable management decisions and improve the reliability of production systems.

The presented research demonstrates the relevance and diversity of approaches to modernizing production management. Integration of innovations, use of analytical models, transparent evaluation systems and resilience analysis methods form the basis for developing comprehensive management strategies in the framework of digital transformation.

The article [11] discusses theoretical aspects and applied approaches to modernizing production systems through management transformation. Emphasis is placed on structural changes in management to improve technical and economic performance. Strategies that ensure enterprises' adaptation to the changing conditions of the external environment using innovative management methods are analyzed.

The study by V.V. Baranov et al. [12] is devoted to developing and implementing an innovative management model that integrates the innovation system into the strategic planning of high-tech enterprises. The authors substantiate the need for a comprehensive approach, including the synthesis of theoretical knowledge and practical tools, to ensure the long-term sustainability of the enterprise in knowledge-intensive production conditions.

M.S. Chemaev's study [13] focuses on analyzing the shortcomings of existing systems for managing production operations. The study demonstrates the need to use mathematical models and analytical methods to optimize processes to improve production systems' efficiency and eliminate organizational dysfunctions.

The article by A.Yu. Sirotkin [14] studies transformation of production systems with a focus on the economic essence of modernization. It considers methodological approaches that allow developing management strategies, including risk analysis, rationalizing resource potential, and implementing innovative technological solutions. The work is focused on implementing strategies to increase industrial enterprises' competitiveness.

The research [15] aims to study the influence of human capital on industrial performance. It considers innovative mechanisms of personnel management which contribute to the intellectualization of processes and improve their manageability. The work emphasizes the importance of forming effective human resource management systems adapted to industrial production tasks.

E.N. Syshchikova [16] proposes a conceptual model for modernizing the management of knowledge-intensive enterprises based on cognitive approaches, philosophical foundations, and integration of digital technologies. The research is focused on developing an adaptive management system capable of meeting the challenges of a high-tech economy, which is relevant in the conditions of digital transformation.

Modernizing the production control system is essential to increasing efficiency, reducing costs, and improving product quality. Some key areas that can be considered for modernization are process automation, the Internet of Things, data analytics, flexible manufacturing systems, sustainable production, personnel training and development, quality management systems, and digitalization.

Each of these areas can be adapted depending on the specifics of the industry and the needs of a particular enterprise. This is already happening in the metallurgical sector [17], agriculture [18; 19] and processing of agricultural products [20], production systems [21], and development of support software [22; 23].

The analysis of the studied sources demonstrates the diversity of theoretical and practical approaches used to modernize the management of production systems. The studies cover using digital technologies, developing intelligent algorithms, optimizing human capital, and creating adaptive management models. Such approaches form the basis for improving management strategies in the face of technological and economic change.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Modernization of production management is based on an interdisciplinary approach that combines analytical tools, economic and mathematical modeling and digital technologies. Data analysis, optimization modeling, and algorithmic calculation methods are applied to achieve the set objectives. Particular emphasis is placed on developing production performance evaluation indicators including resource costs, operational parameters and time characteristics of production processes.

Methods applied include:

- Optimization approaches aimed to analyze the enterprise's resource potential and reduce costs to ensure the achievement of target production indicators.

Cluster analysis methods are used to identify groups of processes with similar characteristics and optimize their parameters.

- Econometric models based on regression algorithms to analyze the dependence of production indicators on internal and external factors.

Methods integrating managerial, economic and technological parameters are developed for complex production systems. In the framework of the study, the author's approach to calculating key indicators characterizing production adaptability and sustainability to changes in the external environment is proposed. The basis of this approach is an analytical toolkit that allows for a quantitative assessment of the impact of modernization on the economic efficiency of the enterprise.

The key element of the proposed methodology is the model for assessing the efficiency of production management. The coefficient of production resources efficiency, defined by Formula 1, is used as a basic indicator:

$$K_{eff} = \frac{P}{R + C}, \quad (1)$$

where:

K_{eff} is coefficient of production resources efficiency;

P is total production productivity;

R is total resource costs;

C is costs associated with modernization.

To assess the level of adaptation of the production system to the changing parameters of the external environment, the adaptability coefficient is used, calculated by Formula 2:

$$K_{adapt} = \frac{\Delta E}{\Delta T}, \quad (2)$$

where:

K_{adapt} is adaptability coefficient;

ΔE is change in production efficiency for a certain period;

ΔT is time interval of changes.

To analyze the integration of digital technologies into production, a digitalization indicator is developed, defined as the ratio of digital infrastructure costs to the total volume of investment:

$$I_{digit} = \frac{D_{inv}}{I_{total}}, \quad (3)$$

where:

I_{digit} is digitalization indicator;

D_{inv} is investments in digital infrastructure;

I_{total} is total investment volume.

The author's stress testing methodology is used to diagnose production systems stability under the variability of external factors. This method aims to identify key vulnerabilities in resource management and assess the sensitivity of production parameters to changes in the market environment, resource availability and technological transformations. The basis of the stress testing model is to analyze the sensitivity of key efficiency ratios to fluctuations in external variables.

All calculations and modeling are performed using the Python programming language. Program implementation relies on Pandas, NumPy, and SciPy libraries for data processing and Scikit-learn for building predictive models and sensitivity analysis. The analysis is based on a representative sample of production indicators collected from enterprises in various sectors of the economy.

The methods proposed in the study form the basis for developing an integrated algorithm for modernizing production management. The algorithm covers aspects such as rationalizing resource costs, modeling operational processes, and quantitative assessment of the system's adaptability to changes in the external environment. Applying an integrated approach contributes to improving the performance of production activities and minimizing economic risks associated with the variability of external conditions.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The developed methodology for modernizing production management was tested within the research framework. The main focus was analyzing the adaptability and sustainability of production systems and assessing the impact of digitalization on their performance. The results are presented as quantitative indicators reflecting the effectiveness of the proposed approaches.

The coefficient, calculated based on changes in production efficiency and time interval, was used to assess the adaptability of production systems. The dynamics of the indicator are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Dynamics of the indicator of production systems adaptability

Period	Production efficiency (E)	Time interval (T), days	Adaptability coefficient
2018	85.4	180	0.474
2019	91.7	190	0.483
2020	88.2	185	0.477
2021	94.5	200	0.473
2022	97.1	210	0.462

The analysis of the indicators dynamics demonstrated the preservation of a stable level of adaptability of production systems, which indicates their ability to maintain efficiency in the face of Changes in environmental parameters.

To study the level of digitalization of processes, the digitalization indicator was applied, based on the ratio of expenditures for developing digital infrastructure to the total investment of the enterprise. The results of the calculation are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Dynamics of the indicator of production systems digitalization

Year	Digital infrastructure costs, million rubles	Total investments, million RUR	Digitalization indicator
2018	120	500	0.24
2019	135	530	0.25
2020	150	570	0.26
2021	170	600	0.28
2022	200	650	0.31

The digitalization indicator shows a steady upward trend, reflecting increased investment in digital infrastructure and the gradual introduction of digital technologies in managing production processes.

Stress testing methodology was applied to assess the resilience of production systems. The analysis aimed to determine the sensitivity of key production parameters to changes in external factors such as market fluctuations, resource availability and technological changes. The results of stress testing are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3

Results of stress testing of production systems

Factor	Normative value	Deviation from the norm (%)	Effect on efficiency (%)
Market conditions	1.00	±15	±12
Raw material availability	1.00	±10	±8
Innovative technologies	1.00	±20	±15

The analysis results confirmed that the most significant impact on production performance is caused by changes related to introducing innovative technologies. This indicates the need to focus on developing and implementing technological innovations aimed at improving the competitiveness of production systems.

The obtained data confirm the effectiveness of the proposed methodology. Using the developed models allows for the detailed analysis of production processes, identification of areas of vulnerability, and proposal of strategies to improve adaptability and sustainability. The developed approaches lay the foundation for further improvement of production systems management in digital transformation conditions and technological complexity growth.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The analysis of modernizing the production systems management in the framework of digital transformation confirmed the need to develop integrative methodologies that combine mathematical modeling, digital analytics, and adaptive management approaches. The results demonstrate the significance of using quantitative analysis methods to assess the adaptability and sustainability of production systems and the impact of digitalization on their performance.

One of the main conclusions is the effectiveness of using the digitalization indicator and the adaptability coefficient to assess performance and identify areas for improving production processes. The positive dynamics of the digitalization indicator shows the increasing importance of investments in digital infrastructure, which confirms the need for their prioritization in strategic planning.

Approval of the stress testing methodology revealed the most sensitive parameters of production systems vulnerable to changes in the market environment and technological transformations. This allows considering external factors in planning production processes, increasing their adaptability. The analysis results indicate the need to develop long-term strategies to improve the sustainability of systems by strengthening their technological potential.

Applying the proposed models and analytical methods forms the basis for rethinking traditional approaches to managing production systems. The totality of the obtained data confirms the possibility of integrating adaptive management approaches and digital technologies into the strategy of enterprises in various industries. This contributes to improving the efficiency and competitiveness of production systems.

The scientific and methodological contribution of the research lies in developing analytical tools focused on the comprehensive study of production under the conditions of variability of the external environment. The practical significance of the work lies in the possibility of applying the developed models to optimize management and improve the sustainability of production systems, which is especially relevant in the framework of digital transformation and technological progress.

Further development of the methodology involves integrating machine learning and big data methods to create predictive models capable of considering the complex interrelationships between economic, technological and organizational parameters. The research opens up prospects for forming integrated management strategies capable of responding to the challenges of the external environment and increasing the adaptive capabilities of production systems.

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